

PRODUCTIVITY AND PROFITABILITY OF FORAGES *VIS-A-VIS* THEIR EFFECT ON SOIL NUTRIENT STATUS IN ORGANIC BLACK COTTON SOILS OF CENTRAL INDIAP. P. Kamble¹, N. W. Raut¹, P. S. Solunke¹, S.M. Sawadhakar¹, A. D. Jejal¹Department of Agronomy, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola (Maharashtra)²Agronomy Section, ICAR – National Dairy Research Institute, Karnal (Haryana)

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Abstract

About 20.5 million peoples in our country are depend upon livestock for their livelihood. Therefore, this sector has also an important contribution in Indian economy with 28.6% of total agricultural GDP (GoI, 2023-24). Presently India is holding number one position in livestock population as well as in milk production but the productivity point of view we are harvested only 987 kg/lactation yield; which has wide gap in per lactation yield as compared to world average (2038 kg/lactation yield) and European countries (6941 kg/lactation yield). Behind this poor productivity and performance of Indian animals so many factors are responsible, among these factors one important factor is unavailability of sufficient quality feed and fodder to animal timely for getting best performance. At present India is having only 5.4% (8.4 Mha) of the cultivated area under forage crops, which has resulted in a severe deficit of green fodder (12%), dry crop residues (24%) and concentrate feed ingredients (27%) (Annual Report, NDDDB, 2024). To maintain or raise the performance of current available livestock population and its productivity, we need to enhance the quality forage production and its productivity to achieve minimum optimum balanced feeding of livestock's. Feeding in dairy farming is the utmost important management factor because it is attributed to around 65-70% of the total input cost of animals (Makkar, 2016).

Keywords - Productivity and Profitability, livestock population, dairy farming.

Introduction:

Surve et al. (2011) also reported that availability of green fodder with good quality is the key to success of dairy enterprises and without supply of quality fodder it is difficult to maintain the health and milk production level of the animals. Green fodder production is only single and cheap component in order to reduce the total input cost of milk production and make the dairy enterprises more profitable. In respect to enhance the availability of fodder and forage, area intensification is difficult task because it faces severe competition with other commercial enterprises and food crops. Therefore, only one and one suitable and feasible alternative remained under present context is to boost up the productivity of fodder and forage crop per unit area as well as per unit time. In many studies it has well established that perennials grasses (like Napier, guinea, paragrass etc.) have more yield advantage in comparison to annual forage crops because it requires lower input and it also uniformly supply high green biomass in continuous manner for longtime periods. Napier bajra hybrid (NBH) and guinea grass are important forage grasses of the tropics and well known for its higher biomass potential, palatability, persistence and for quality fodder. In most cases the nutritional quality of cereal fodder is lower as compared to legume. The nutritional quality of cereal fodder or grasses can be enhanced either by mixing legume or growing of legume as inter/mix crop infield condition itself. Another major advantage of inclusion of legume with grasses is to sustain the soil health Halli et al. (2018). Baby corn (*Zea mays* L.) is also important dual-purpose crop grown for premature cob as well as green fodder near to peri-urban and urban areas dairy farmers. Its dual importance and fast-growing habit, high biomass yield potential, better nutritional quality and palatability, absence of any anti-quality compound all these

characteristics are make it farmer choice for dairy enterprises. It is therefore, imperative to evaluate the best forage crop or crop combination which are maximize the productivity as well as profitability of dairy farmers in Central India. Hence, keeping these things in view the present investigations was undertaken.

Materials And Methods

The present study was carried out during *kharif* 2023 at Centre for Organic Agriculture Research and Training, Department of Agronomy, Dr Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, Maharashtra located at 20.7002° North latitude, 77.0082° East longitudes and at an altitude of 245 m above mean sea level (MSL). The region witnesses sub-tropical, sub-humid climate with hot summers. The meteorological phenomenon occurred during study period (July, 2023-November, 2023) are furnished in Table 1, rainfall and evapotranspiration also furnished in Fig 1. The maximum temperature was recorded 34°C in 29th standard week, while minimum temperature remained 31.7°C during the study period.

The soil of experimental plot was black cotton soils (vertisol) in texture with chemically basic reaction 8.4 pH, medium in Walkley-Black C (0.49%), EC (1:2) (0.17 dS/m), low in KMnO₄ Oxidizable N (205 kg/ha) and 0.5 M NaHCO₃- extractable P (14.23 kg/ha), and high 1N NH₄OAC extractable K (328.34 kg/ha). The experiment was laid out in randomized complete block design (RCBD) with four replications perennial forage crops Napier bajra hybrid/NBH (DHN 10 & Phule Jaywant), Maize (African tall), Sorghum (AKSSV 22 & Vasudha), Foxtail (PDKV Yashashri), Lucerne (Rajka). The crops were sown as per crop standard agronomical package and practices. A common dose of well decomposed farm yard manure (FYM) @ 10 t/ha has been applied three weeks prior to sowing of the crops. Nutrient management

is done through organic conditions.

Fig 1: Weekly average meteorological observations chart during study period.

Observations on biometric growth parameters were recorded at 30 days after sowing (DAS) and at the time of harvest. The 1st cut was taken for fodder at 60 days after planting or DAS in NBH, guinea grass and cowpea, sorghum and maize while baby corn was harvested at 65 DAS. For harvesting of cob 2-3 manual picking is required in 2-3 days intervals. The 2nd cut was taken for the NBH, guinea grass and for multicut sorghum at 30-35 Days after 1st cutting. At each harvesting plant samples (1.0 kg fresh weight) were collected to analyse quality parameters. To assess dry matter (DM) contents, all samples were dried in a hot air oven at 65°C for at least 48 hour until a constant weight was reached. The dried samples were milled to pass through a 2 mm sieve for nutritional quality evaluation. The net profit per ha was calculated by deducting the cost of cultivation from the gross returns per ha.

Results And Discussion

Green Yield

At the first Cut: The highest cumulative yield of green forage was recorded in T5 (Sorghum cv Vasudha) with 326.14 q ha⁻¹, followed by T3 (Sorghum cv AKSSV-22) with 317.08 q ha⁻¹, and T2 (Maize cv African Tall) with 302.5 q ha⁻¹. T7 (Hy. Napier cv DHN 10) showed 155.93 q ha⁻¹, and T6 (Hy. Napier cv Phule Jaywant) had 137.17 q ha⁻¹. T1 (Foxtail cv PDKV Yashashri) recorded 66.67 q ha⁻¹, while T4 (Lucern cv Rajka) had the lowest at 30.22 q ha⁻¹.

At the second cut: T5 (Sorghum cv Vasudha) again showed the highest cumulative yield with 314.88 q ha⁻¹, followed by T3 (Sorghum cv AKSSV-22) with 312.64 q ha⁻¹. T7 (Hy. Napier cv DHN 10) recorded 295.67 q ha⁻¹, while T2 (Maize cv African Tall) yielded 290.2 q ha⁻¹. T6 (Hy. Napier cv Phule Jaywant) showed 208.67 q ha⁻¹, T1 (Foxtail cv PDKV Yashashri) produced 71.05 q ha⁻¹, and T4 (Lucern cv Rajka) yielded 35.4 q ha⁻¹.

Total Yield: T5 (Sorghum cv Vasudha) recorded the highest total green forage yield with 641.02 q ha⁻¹, followed by T3 (Sorghum cv AKSSV-22) with 629.72 q ha⁻¹. T2 (Maize cv African Tall) yielded 592.7 q ha⁻¹, T7 (Hy. Napier cv DHN 10) produced 451.6 q ha⁻¹, and T6 (Hy. Napier cv Phule Jaywant) had 345.83 q ha⁻¹. T1 (Foxtail cv PDKV Yashashri) recorded the lowest total yield at 137.72 q ha⁻¹, followed by T4 (Lucern cv Rajka) with 65.62 q ha⁻¹.

These results show that Sorghum varieties (T3 and T5) produced the highest cumulative yields of green forage, followed by Maize (T2) and Hy. Napier varieties (T6 and T7). Foxtail and Lucern produced significantly lower yields compared to the other crops. The same findings were reported by Das et al (2016) Bhade et al. (2002)

Crude Protein:

Among the treatments, the highest crude protein percentage was observed in T4 (Lucern cv Rajka), recording 18.72%, which significantly surpassed all other treatments. Following Lucern, T5 (Sorghum cv Vasudha) exhibited a notable crude protein content of 12.44%. T6 (Hy. Napier cv Phule Jaywant) and T3 (Sorghum cv AKSSV-22) also showed relatively high crude protein percentages, at 11.8% and 11.48%, respectively.

Moderate levels of crude protein were recorded in T7 (Hy. Napier cv DHN 10) with 10.86% and T2 (Maize cv African Tall) with 9.3%. The lowest crude protein content was found in T1 (Foxtail cv PDKV Yashashri), with a value of 7.48%.

The variation in crude protein percentages among treatments highlights the influence of species and cultivar characteristics on protein accumulation. Lucern cv Rajka exhibited the highest protein content, likely due to its leguminous nature, which typically enhances nitrogen fixation and protein synthesis. In contrast, the relatively lower protein levels in non-leguminous species like Maize and Foxtail indicate differences in nutrient uptake. The same findings were reported by Bama et al.(2013)

Soil Physio Chemical Properties

Nitrogen:

The highest available nitrogen content after harvest was observed in T4 (Lucern cv Rajka) with 270 kg ha⁻¹, followed by T5 (Sorghum cv Vasudha) with 214 kg ha⁻¹. The other treatments had nitrogen levels ranging from 198 kg ha⁻¹ in T2 (Maize cv African Tall) to 206.33 kg ha⁻¹ in T3 (Sorghum cv AKSSV-22). The overall average for nitrogen was 214.29 kg ha⁻¹, which was slightly lower than the initial nitrogen content of 215.4 kg ha⁻¹.

Phosphorus:

Phosphorus levels were similar across treatments, with T2 (Maize cv African Tall) having the highest available phosphorus at 15.37 kg ha⁻¹. The other treatments had phosphorus values ranging from 14.1 to 14.97 kg ha⁻¹. The overall average for phosphorus was 14.51 kg ha⁻¹, which is slightly lower than the initial phosphorus content of 16.4 kg ha⁻¹.

Potassium:

The highest potassium content was recorded in T7 (Hy. Napier cv DHN 10) at 332.33 kg ha⁻¹, followed by T4 (Lucern cv Rajka) with 330.33 kg ha⁻¹. The other treatments had potassium values ranging from 324.67 kg ha⁻¹ (T3) to 326.67 kg ha⁻¹ (T5). The overall average potassium level was 327.57 kg ha⁻¹, which is almost the same as the initial potassium content of 325.4 kg ha⁻¹.

These results show slight variations in nutrient levels among the different forage crops, with no major depletion or increase in soil nutrient content after harvest. The soil's nutrient status remained relatively stable across the treatments, with small differences in nitrogen and phosphorus levels compared to the initial values. Similar results were obtained by Bama et al (2015)

pH:

The pH values across all treatments were similar, ranging from 8.37 to 8.43, indicating slightly alkaline soil conditions. The overall average pH was 8.4, which is slightly higher than the initial pH of 8.35. The pH variation across treatments is minimal, suggesting that the different forage crops did not significantly alter the soil's acidity or alkalinity.

Electrical Conductivity (EC):

The electrical conductivity (EC) values were also quite consistent across the treatments, ranging from 0.17 to 0.18 dsm⁻¹. The overall average EC was 0.18 dsm⁻¹, slightly higher than the initial EC value of 0.17 dsm⁻¹. This suggests that the soil salinity remained stable after harvest, with no significant increase in electrical conductivity from the different treatments.

Organic Carbon (OC):

The organic carbon content after harvest ranged from 4.9 g kg⁻¹ across most treatments, with the exception of T1 (Foxtail cv PDKV Yashashri), which had 4.95 g kg⁻¹. The overall average organic carbon content was 4.91 g kg⁻¹, which is slightly higher than the initial organic carbon content of 4.8 g kg⁻¹. This indicates a small increase in soil organic carbon, possibly due to the decomposition of crop residues or organic matter contributions from the different forage crops.

In conclusion, the soil chemical status after harvest showed only slight variations in pH, EC, and organic carbon content compared to the initial values, indicating that the forage crops did not significantly alter the soil's chemical properties.

Productivity

The data on the economic performance of various forage crops were compiled in terms of Cumulative Yield, Gross Monetary Return (GMR), Cost of Cultivation (COC), Net Monetary Return (NMR), and Benefit-Cost (BC) Ratio, as shown in the table 29. Below is a detailed analysis of the results

Cumulative Green Fodder Yield

Among the treatments, Sorghum cv. Vasudha (T5) recorded the highest cumulative green fodder yield 641.02 q ha⁻¹ and Hybrid Napier cv. DHN 10 (T7) with (451.6 q ha⁻¹), followed by Hybrid Napier cv. Phule Jaywant (T6) with 345.8 q ha⁻¹. Sorghum cv. AKSSV-22 (T3) produced 314.9 q ha⁻¹, respectively. Maize cv. African Tall (T2) yielded 296.4 q ha⁻¹, while Foxtail cv. PDKV Yashashri (T1) and Lucerne cv. Rajka (T4) recorded the lowest cumulative yields of 137.7 q ha⁻¹ and 65.6 q ha⁻¹, respectively.

The superior performance of Hybrid Napier cv. DHN 10 (T7) and Sorghum cv. Vasudha (T5) can be attributed to its perennial nature and high tillering ability, which resulted in sustained productivity across multiple harvests. The significantly lower yield of Lucerne cv. Rajka (T4) may be due to its lower biomass accumulation capacity compared to grasses and cereals.

Gross Monetary Returns (GMR)

The significantly highest GMR was obtained from Sorghum cv. Vasudha (T5) at (Rs 214094 ha⁻¹) followed by Hybrid Napier cv. DHN 10 (T7) at Rs. 150,834 ha⁻¹, followed by Hybrid Napier cv. Phule Jaywant (T6) at Rs. 115,508 ha⁻¹. Sorghum cv. AKSSV-22 (T3) also recorded high GMR of Rs. Rs. 105,163 ha⁻¹. The lowest GMR was observed in Lucerne cv. Rajka (T4) (Rs. 39,372 ha⁻¹) and Foxtail cv. PDKV Yashashri (T1) (Rs. 45,997 ha⁻¹)

Cost of Cultivation (COC)

The cost of cultivation varied among the different treatments. Hybrid Napier cultivars (T6 and T7) incurred the highest cultivation costs (Rs. 85,333 ha⁻¹), followed by Sorghum cv. Vasudha (T5) at Rs. 64,200 ha⁻¹. The lowest cultivation costs were recorded for Lucerne cv. Rajka (T4) (Rs. 32,600 ha⁻¹) and Foxtail cv. PDKV Yashashri (T1) (Rs. 42,400 ha⁻¹). The higher cultivation costs in Hybrid Napier treatments can be attributed to their requirement for intensive management, frequent harvests and nutrient application.

Net Monetary Returns (NMR)

The highest NMR was obtained from Sorghum cv. Vasudha (T5) at Rs 149894 ha⁻¹ followed by Hybrid Napier cv. DHN 10 (T7) at Rs. 65,501 ha⁻¹ followed by Sorghum cv. AKSSV-22 (T3) at Rs. 48,643 ha⁻¹ and Maize cv. African Tall (T2) at Rs. 43,781 ha⁻¹. The lowest NMR was recorded for Foxtail cv. PDKV Yashashri (T1) (Rs. 3,597 ha⁻¹), indicating its lower profitability compared to other crops.

Benefit-Cost (B:C) Ratio

The highest B:C ratio was observed in Sorghum cv. Vasudha (T5) at 3.33 followed by Sorghum cv. AKSSV-22 (T3) at 1.86, followed by Maize cv. African Tall (T2) at 1.79 and Hybrid Napier cv. DHN 10 (T7) at 1.77. The lowest B:C ratio was recorded for Foxtail cv. PDKV Yashashri (T1) at 1.08. The higher B:C ratios in Sorghum and Maize

treatments indicate their economic viability, as they provided higher returns relative to the investment.

Conclusion

For higher economic efficiency and income generation with in short period's Hybrid Napier (DHN 10) cultivation could be a best option. With sorghum multicut varieties But for running the dairy enterprises supply of quality green fodder in a continuous manner with low maintenance cost and high profitability growing of Napier and lucern grass would be better option to others treatments. Therefore, earning of more profit from dairy enterprises it may be advised to a farmer to grow combination of napier grass sorghum varieties with lucern for more feasible, low maintenance, high productivity and continuous supply of quality green fodder.

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Parameters	Net Plot	Spacing	Fertilizer (RDF)	Seed Rate	Variety
Hybrid Napier	4.0 X 8.0 m	100 cm X 100 cm	60:00:00 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ per cutting	33,333 two budded stem cutting ha ⁻¹	DHN-10, Phule Jaywant,
Maize	5.40 X 9.7 m	30 X15 cm	80:30:20kg NPK ha ⁻¹	40 Kg ha ⁻¹	African Tall
Foxtail Millet	5.5 X 9.8 m	20 X10 cm	40:20:20 kg NPK ha ⁻¹	8 Kg ha ⁻¹	PDKV Yashashri
Sorghum	5.40 X 9.80 m	30 X 10 cm	80:40:00 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ Single Cut 100:60:00 Kg NPK ha ⁻¹ Multi cut	8 Kg ha ⁻¹	AKSSV-22 Vasudha
Lucerne	5.40 X 9.90 m	30 X 5 cm	20:40:40 Kg NPK. ha ⁻¹	20 Kg ha ⁻¹	Rajka

Treatment wise quantity of organic input will be applied as per the Nutrient content in the organic sources

Table 1. Basic Experimental Details

Treatment	Economics(Rs ha ⁻¹)			
	GMR	COC	NMR	BC Ratio
T1: Foxtail cv PDKV Yashashri	45997	42400	3597	1.08
T2: Maize cv African Tall	98981	55200	43781	1.79
T3: Sorghum cv AKSSV	105163	56520	48643	1.86
T4: Lucern cv Rajka	39372	32600	6772	1.21
T5: Sorghum cv Vasudha	214094	64200	149894	3.33
T6: Hy. Napier cv Phule Jaywant	115508	85333	30175	1.35
T7: Hy. Napier cv DHN 10	150834	85333	65501	1.77

Table 2. Cumulative yield of green fodder as affected by various treatments

Table 3. Productivity dynamics of various treatment under organic conditions

Treatment	Cumulative yield of green forage (q ha ⁻¹)		
	1 cut	2 cut	Total yield
T1: Foxtail cv PDKV Yashashri	66.67	71.05	137.72
T2: Maize cv African Tall	302.50	290.20	592.70
T3: Sorghum cv AKSSV	317.08	312.63	629.72
T4: Lucern cv Rajka	30.22	35.40	65.62
T5: Sorghum cv Vasudha	326.14	314.88	641.02
T6: Hy. Napier cv Phule Jaywant	137.17	208.67	345.83
T7: Hy. Napier cv DHN 10	155.93	295.67	451.60